

THE EMERGENCE AND DEVELOPMENT OF PAPER PRODUCTION IN CENTRAL ASIA

Goyibova Sayyora Usmonovna
Teacher of Namangan state university
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10984699>

O'RTA OSIYODA QOG'OZ ISHLAB CHIQRISHNING PAYDO BO'LISHI VA RIVOJLANISHI

G'oyibova Sayyora Usmonovna
Namangan davlat universiteti o'qituvchisi

ВОЗНИКНОВЕНИЕ И РАЗВИТИЕ БУМАЖНОГО ПРОИЗВОДСТВА В СРЕДНЕЙ АЗИИ

Гойибова Сайёра Усмоновна
Преподаватель Наманганского государственного университета

Annotation: This article provides detailed information about the production process of the first paper, the process of paper production in Chinese sources, the appearance of paper in Central Asia, the quality and development of Samarkand papers.

Keywords: paper, production, country, city, history, source, progress, development, quality, wood, silk fabrics.

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada dastlabki qog'ozning ishlab chiqarish jarayoni, xitoy manbalarida qog'oz ishlab chiqarish jarayonining yoritilishi, O'rta Osiyoga qog'ozni paydo bo'lishi, Samarqand qog'ozlarning sifati va rivojlanishi haqida batafsil ma'lumot berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: qog'oz, ishlab chiqarish, mamlakat, shahar, tarix, manba, taraqqiyot, rivojlanish, sifat, yog'och, ipak matolar.

Аннотация: В данной статье представлены подробные сведения о процессе производства первой бумаги, процессе производства бумаги в китайских источниках, появлении бумаги в Средней Азии, качестве и развитии самаркандских бумаг.

Ключевые слова: бумага, производство, страна, город, история, источник, прогресс, развитие, качество, древесина, шелковые ткани.

The emergence of paper production is parallel to the development of world culture with the discovery of different types of writing, from pictorial ideographic forms to alphabets in ancient and medieval times. Papermaking according to its importance is textile, gunpowder, hand mill, water mill, clock, book copying by means of woodcut molds, free-rolling wooden road. It is comparable to such universal inventions as letterforms and printing. It is an undoubted historical phenomenon that paper itself has appeared as a writing material, a symbol of culture and literacy, as a means of recording the various manifestations of the spiritual world of mankind for more than two thousand years. the historical homeland of paper is considered to be China. There is no exact information in science about the time of its discovery. [1]. It is not known who discovered it. But according to Chinese sources, boiling a

ball of silk fibers in water and applying the resulting porridge thinly on a hard flat surface board.

Paper or similar writing materials were made as early as the last centuries BC by pressing the dried leaves with a hammer and smoothing the edges. The earliest written information about paper dates back to 12 AD in Chinese sources. Its use in bookkeeping must be chronologically close to this time. Including. There is information that the book was written on paper in 76 AD. During the excavation of an archaeological monument belonging to the Han Dynasty, located on the banks of the Etzinakhe River in Northeast China, pieces of paper with writing were found. They have year timestamps, the oldest date is 93 years and the latest date is 98 years. [2]. Herbalists examined this paper and concluded that its basis is indeed plant fibers. During the archeological excavation of the ruins of the ancient village of Edzingol near Khara-Khoto, it was found that the dates of the silk cloth wraps and wooden boards found along with a piece of paper were 94-98 AD. Based on these and other findings, the Chinese archaeologist Lao Kang concluded that the production time of Edzingol paper was not later than 98 years. The intactness of the archaeological layers also precludes the possibility of accidental slippage of paper between them. Therefore, the paper used for the Edzingol inscriptions was produced in the second half of the first century AD [3]. The exact date of the appearance of paper in Turonzamin, the initial stage of paper production and the ways of development have not yet been described in detail. Researches about this are few and do not rely on specific historical sources. In a word, the history of Turanian paper has not been sufficiently studied until now.

Bamboo boards have been used as a material in the history and production of paper. Later, for mass use, a valuable material-locked silk fabric was used. Pieces of silk fabric were widely used in II-I centuries BC. These fragments are placed on the surface of the board to obtain a felt-like brittle material that becomes papery when dry. Researcher N. Khabibullaev, who specially studied the production technology, which is now relatively cheap and is the first ancestor of the paper of the next era, writes that "the question of the emergence of paper production in Central Asia has not yet been determined. In this field, the opinions of my researchers do not come close to each other, this issue still needs to be carefully studied again and again. professor A. Semyonov in his scientific work dedicated to the history of paper made a scientific hypothesis that paper production was practiced in Samarkand and its surroundings long before the Arab conquest, and this city was a high-quality paper-making center from ancient times. In particular, he writes: "...Samarkand has long been famous for working with excellent silk paper. Samarkand paper mills were known in 650-651 at the initial stage when the Arabs began to conquer Khorasan and Central Asia..." Apparently. Arab caliphate. and later, the emergence of paper production throughout Europe was caused by the mastering of Samarkand stationery [4]. In any case, the high quality of Samarkand paper brought it fame, and this work was carried out at a high level in the following centuries. According to the report given by a Persian source of the 10th century, Samarkand paper was taken to different countries of the world. In the 11th century, Persian poets, apparently, highly described the paper workshops of Samarkand, which were famous at that time, in their poems. According to historical sources, the history of paper production in Central Asia by the Chinese people is the first in Turonzamin As the paper became an integral part of the Chinese culture, the use of paper along the Great Silk Road became more and more widespread. in the

Sughd trade villages (trading factories) that became infrastructure, and then it became common in all regions of Turan. in particular. It was written to relatives in Samarkand and other cities. 9 Sugdian letters sent in the years 312-317 (these letters are called "Old Sugdian letters" in science) were written on Chinese paper of the first period. So. it can be said that the people of Samarkand and Bukhara knew paper already in the 3rd century. Moreover. During the archaeological excavations in Eastern Turkestan at the beginning of the 20th century, many letters, documents, paper books and fragments of them, and cover fragments were found. This indicates that Chinese paper began to spread outside of China in the first centuries AD (II-III) [5]. Probably, along with Korea, the countries of Sughd and Bactria became a foreign trade market for Chinese paper. In the ruins of the city of Kucha, archaeologists found complete leather covers. They are Manichean religious book covers. estimated to belong to the IV century AD. It is known that paper was used in the production of books in the communities of Manichean faith in Eastern and Western Turkestan as early as the 4th century.

In 1932-1933, from the ruins of the early medieval castle named Kalai Mugh, located on the upper reaches of the Zarafshan River, 22 of my documents, which were part of the archive of the kings and officials of Sughd, consisting of a total of 80 Sughd documents, were written on paper (the rest are leather, oil). in materials such as). This case shows that paper was widely used in the sphere of public administration of Sughd in the end of the 7th century - beginning of the 8th century. Governors of Panjikent Chakin Chur Bilga (700-708). During the period of Devashtich (708-722), Sugd king Tarkhun (700-710), Gorak (710-738 villas), paper had a strong place among other writing materials. Text number A-5 from the documents of the Mugh Castle contains a list of various expenses of Devashtich Palace. The money spent was called a drachma. It is a silver coin with an original size of 4.25 g. equal to silver. According to the document, with this money, 8 drachmas were given for paper and silk cloth. So, at the beginning of the VII-VIII centuries, there was a paper market in Samarkand and Bukhara, where paper was not only brought from China, but also made there. is also available for sale. There is no doubt that the Ughds directly adopted the Chinese method of paper production. On the one hand, this appropriation is reliably evidenced by the scope of historical and cultural relations between the peoples, and on the other hand, it is confirmed by the fact that the tradition of using paper in Samarkand and Bukhara has a long history. In addition, the paper production technology of the people of Turkestan was either the same as the Chinese technology or a slightly improved form of this method. A Russian tourist said that Ukrainian masters used the Chinese method of paper production and developed it. The testimony written by A. Fedchenko, a researcher of Central and Central Asia, is very interesting. [6]. A. Fedchenko was in Kokand in the last quarter of the 19th century and saw the paper workshops built outside the Muyimubarak gate of the city. He writes about his impressions like this: "I accidentally got acquainted with the Chinese method of paper production. When I saw the Objuvoz (a water mill used for pulping and crushing paper pulp - E.O.) in Kok, I was struck by its exact similarity with paper making in China". Commenting on this observation of A.P. Fedchenko, prof. A. Semyonov says: "...This production has its roots in the Chinese method before Islam. But it preserved the characteristics of the Chinese method of paper making until recent times... It is not surprising. The masters of Central Asia preserved the

Chinese traditions and skill forms in paper production. Regardless of the primitive and ancient methods of manual work, they brought the quality of paper to such a high level that even today's factory paper production cannot meet this quality requirement. Papermaking methods and skills have been a family livelihood of artisans for hundreds of years, passed down from generation to generation. To tell the truth, Kokan masters have forgotten some aspects of the most ancient technology. But processing the pulp, the ways of getting paper sheets from it remained unchanged. The Sugdian word "kogziak", which began to be practically forgotten by the 11th century, proves that paper making and use in the Uron region is ancient. This was the ancient derivation of the word paper in our modern language. The word "paper" thus entered Tajik, Persian, Uzbek and many other languages from the Sugdian language. In Arabic, this word exists in the form of "paper". New researches on archeology and history of Ughd, Bactria, Ancient Khorezm, Kushan kingdom. The analysis of the sources on the languages and writings of the ancient peoples of Turan and the points of view expressed in the scientific literature on paper production show that the first paper production in our country dates back to the early Middle Ages. As a writing material, paper entered the Sughd culture from the 3rd century. This was the period when paper began to be produced in large quantities in China. Papermaking also spread to Xinjiang at this time. The Sugdians directly adopted the paper production from the Chinese. The spread of paper in early medieval Turan, both through the market and through the spread of production and technology, society's needs for paper.

It happened in connection with the consistency of our relations with China in the fields of trade and culture. Sugdians and Turkic peoples played a decisive historical position in this matter. Due to the quality change of the social and cultural life of the Turanian peoples after the Arab occupation, the need for paper increased. Paper production began to spread from Samarkand to other cities of Turonzamin. Paper workshops first began to appear in cities where cultural life flourished. Between the 9th and 10th centuries, paper workshops appeared in cities such as Balkh, Marv, Termiz, Gurganch, Khiva, and Tashkent. At different times, this work was carried out in these cities at different levels. At the beginning of the 18th century, the first paper workshops appeared in Kok. They were organized by artisans who fled from Samarkand to the Ferghana Valley due to feudal disputes, endless torture and oppression that made the people suffer, and invasions. At the end of the 18th century, Samarkand to Bukhara became depressed. In Turonzamin, its center remained Kokan. During the 19th century and at the beginning of the 20th century, Kokan distributed papers to all parts of Turkistan. Kokan paper was also published abroad. About this, A. Semyonov says: "After the paper production stopped in centers like Samarkand and Bukhara, Kokan began to dominate all the centers of the former Russian Turkestan with paper, from China to the Aral Sea. (Kokan paper was exported to Kashkar and even to Northern Afgkhanistan)." With the use of paper in bookmaking, all the possibilities of using Arabic script for decoration and ornamentation and patterns can be fully used. It's done. As a result, in Turonzamin, a unique art of decorating manuscripts with a system of aesthetic rules, a whole set of methods and techniques for copying books and reproducing them in bookstores through the work of a team of masters was created. The main reason for all this was the natural properties of the paper used in bookmaking. The structural structure of the paper, its thin sheet shape, flat surface

made it so convenient for the writing process and for reading the text, for storing the necessary information in written form, moreover, for transferring it across time and space, that its importance is one It is difficult to express in words. The spread of paper printing from Samarkand to the whole of Turonzamin and from there to the Middle East and Europe is a huge historical event and has become a turning point in the world book culture. This situation opened wide possibilities for the production of handwritten books. Local book copying initiated a new phase of book collecting, based on the Arabic script. A new era in the book history of Turonzamin began in connection with paper production. The implementation of paper production in a standard and fixed manner became one of the most important factors that served the firm establishment of the Arabic script in the culture of the Turanian peoples. and in a broader sense. It is very difficult to assess the incomparable role of the Turanian peoples in the cultural development. The production of paper, convenient for writing, cheap compared to leather, but not inferior to it in durability, led to the expansion of the distribution of books in the society. This is the only way to achieve spiritual maturity and a rich cultural and spiritual heritage.[7] The improvement of paper production was one of the first foundations for the production of books by the self-printing method. It would be a mistake to copy Karl Marx's opinion that book printing "laid the ground for bourgeois development" and that the spread of paper production through Turkestan throughout the Muslim world was the ground for the development of medieval and modern culture. Doesn't. In the end, this same paper served to rise to the peak of Muslim culture. In particular, the unprecedented level of the cultural development of Turkestan in the 9th-13th centuries was unimaginable without paper. The emergence of paper factories in Europe at the end of the 13th century and the beginning of the 14th century created the first technological basis for the formation of European book printing in 1445. This phenomenon remains one of the main cornerstones of modern human culture. Over the past period, the Republic of Uzbekistan has adopted a number of normative and legal acts on the development of culture and arts[8].

References:

1. Bibliographic work in the library: organization and methodology: textbook / Ed. O.P. Korshunov. - M.: "Book Chamber" publishing house, 1990. - P. 24.
2. Vaneev A.N. Librarianship. Theory. Methodology. Practice: on the occasion of the author's 80th birthday. - SPb.: KasBibliography- 2004. - P.50
3. Kartashov N.S. General library science: a textbook for students. high. study.institutions: at 2 o'clock / N.S. Kartashov, V.V. Skvortsov. - M.: Moscow. State University of Culture, 2002. - Volume 1: Theoretical foundations of librarianship. - P.28
4. Kartashov NS Comparative librarianship: A textbook for students. high. learning.institutions. - M.; Profizdat, - 2000. - P.54
5. Kogotkov D. Bibliographic activity of the library: organization, technology, management: textbook / D.Ya. Kogotkov. - Bibliography: Profession, 2005. - P.70
6. Matulsky R. General library science: a study guide for universities. - Liberia, - 2004. - P.12
7. Morgenstern I.G Librarianship and Bibliography // Sov. library science. - 1986.-No. 1.- P. 99-104.

7. Мирхакимова, Ф. (2023). МУЗЕЙ КАК ОДИН ИЗ ОЧАГОВ КУЛЬТУРЫ. Общественные науки в современном мире: теоретические и практические исследования, 2(14), 9–11. извлечено от <https://www.inacademy.uz/index.php/zdif/article/view/24049>
8. Mirkhakimova Feruza Kholdorjon kizi. [Activity of Mutal Burkhanov House Museum](#). CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCES AND HISTORY VOLUME: 03 ISSUE: 11 | NOV 2022 (ISSN: 2660-6836). 76-81 pp.